

Machine Learning Enhanced Cosmic-Ray Tomography for Advanced Imaging in Maritime Security

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Abstract— Cosmic-ray tomography represents a new approach for inspection technology — a safe alternative to X-ray and gamma-ray scanners. Methods for muon scattering tomography have been developed by Los Alamos National Laboratory and commercialized by Decision Sciences as the Discovery® scanning system. This cutting-edge system is capable of providing a new tool for customs authorities searching for weapons, explosives, shielded nuclear material, smuggled people and various other contraband. It has been successfully deployed around the globe at ports, border crossings and other places. As the largest commercially available muon tomography scanner, the system accommodates cargo containers on commercial trucks. Using advanced image reconstruction techniques it analyzes signals and generates 3-D images of the scanned items. Learning from previous deployments, we continue to enhance the system's imaging capabilities and extend its reach to new customers. Here we discuss recent advancements in muon tomography technology, focusing on machine learning based approaches to accelerate muon tomography reconstructions, enhancing image quality and interpretation through machine learning algorithms and edge sharpening techniques. Additionally, breakthroughs in passive human detection capability offer promising prospects for improving security measures in maritime environments. These developments signify significant strides in enhancing the efficacy and scope of muon tomography in bolstering maritime security and infrastructure resilience.

Index terms—cosmic-ray tomography, machine learning algorithms, maritime security.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime ports serve as crucial hubs for global trade and transportation, handling vast quantities of goods and commodities every day. With such high traffic volumes, ensuring port security is paramount to safeguarding against potential threats such as the smuggling of weapons, explosives, and illicit materials. Traditional security measures often rely on X-ray and gamma-ray scanners, which pose health risks and operational limitations.

In recent years a revolutionary technology has emerged as a safer and more effective alternative: cosmic-ray tomography [1]. Developed initially by Los Alamos National Laboratory [2] and commercialized by Decision Sciences as the Discovery® scanning system, cosmic-ray tomography harnesses naturally occurring cosmic rays to penetrate and scan cargo containers, offering unparalleled insights into their contents without the need for harmful radiation [3].

This cutting-edge system represents a paradigm shift in port security, providing customs authorities with a powerful tool to detect a wide range of contraband, including weapons, explosives, shielded nuclear material, and even smuggled

humans. Deployed successfully at ports and border crossings, the Discovery® scanning system has demonstrated its efficacy in enhancing security measures while minimizing risks to personnel and the environment [4]. These systems have already been installed around the world with the most recent deployments in Singapore and Abu Dhabi (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Cosmic-ray tomography systems produced by Decision Sciences and installed in ports for maritime security.

As the largest commercially available muon tomography scanner, the system accommodates cargo containers on commercial trucks, facilitating seamless integration into existing port operations. Leveraging advanced image reconstruction techniques, it analyzes signals from cosmic-ray interactions to generate detailed 3-D images of scanned items, enabling authorities to identify anomalies and potential threats with unprecedented precision.

With ongoing efforts to enhance imaging capabilities and expand its deployment to new customers, cosmic-ray tomography is poised to redefine the landscape of port security, offering a proactive and comprehensive approach to safeguarding maritime infrastructure and ensuring the uninterrupted flow of global commerce.

This paper presents our recent work focused on the improvement of image reconstruction algorithms in cosmic-ray tomography systems.

II. METHODS: IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION IN MUON TOMOGRAPHY

Muon tomography is a powerful radiographic technique. Muons are highly penetrating particles, able to pass through many meters of dense materials such as concrete, rock, soil and water. This penetration capability is very useful for imaging the interior of large objects or structures, which would be difficult or impossible to inspect with other radiographic techniques. Muon tomography is a non-destructive and non-invasive technique, which means that it does not require the object or

structure being imaged to be damaged or disassembled. This makes it suitable for looking inside historical or culturally significant objects, as well as objects that are difficult, expensive or dangerous to disassemble. Muon tomography uses natural cosmic rays as the source of radiation, which means that the radiation dose to the object or structure being imaged does not exceed the natural background. Muon imaging is totally safe for operators and for the environment.

At the same time muon tomography also has its limitations. The relatively low flux of cosmic muons at the Earth's surface (~ 1 muon/cm²/min) results in long measurement times and requires large detectors to generate high-quality images. Muon tomography data can be noisy, incomplete, or subject to environmental changes due to its long collection period. The generation of clear images necessitates the use of image reconstruction algorithms, which can be complex and time-consuming.

The radiographic source for muon tomography is provided by cosmic-ray muons. Muons are subatomic particles that are similar to electrons but are about two hundred times more massive. They are part of the lepton family of particles and can be positively or negatively charged with an elementary electric charge. Cosmic-ray muons are muons that originate from primary high-energy cosmic rays, extremely energetic particles from space, typically originating from sources like supernovae, black holes, and other astrophysical phenomena. These primary cosmic-rays interact with atmosphere producing showers of unstable elementary particles. Thanks to their relatively long lifetime of approximately 2.2 microseconds and the lack of strong interactions, muons are the particles that can survive longer and dominate the secondary cosmic-ray particle flux of charged particles at the Earth surface and especially underground.

Muon scattering tomography is based on the multiple scattering of the muons. This effect arises as charged particles, such as protons, electrons, or muons traverse a material and experience repeated small-angle deflections due to interactions with atomic nuclei and electrons. The multiple scattering is described by the Molière theory, which quantifies the angular deviations and transverse displacements of the particle's path as it penetrates the material. These deviations increase with the particle's charge, energy, and the atomic density of the material. As a result, the particle's trajectory becomes less predictable over longer distances, imparting a randomizing effect on its path. While multiple scattering can be a source of background noise in some applications, it also provides valuable information about a material's composition and density, which can be utilized for radiographic imaging. By analyzing the scattering patterns of charged particles, radiographers can deduce critical information about the material's composition, thickness, and density distribution. This technique can be used in both accelerator-based applications such as proton radiography and also in cosmic-ray tomography. The scattering of the muons in the examined material reveals its varying density and internal structure, allowing scientists to create detailed radiographic images.

The cosmic-ray absorption can be also used as a secondary signal in scattering muon tomography applications. As the cosmic rays traverse through various materials, they experience

a decrease in intensity due to interactions with the atomic nuclei and especially electrons in the substance. The penetration length of charged particles in matter, known as range, depends on the particles energy and material properties. Higher-energy particles penetrate further into a material before coming to rest, with a non-linear energy-loss relationship leading to a Bragg peak. Material density plays a significant role, as denser materials with higher atomic numbers result in shorter ranges. Combining absorption measurements with multiple scattering allows to discriminate between different materials, because of the stronger dependence of the scattering on the atomic number. The absorption can also be used as an independent radiographic signal. Cosmic-ray muons, with their high penetrating power, are particularly useful as radiographic probes for larger and denser structures, whether natural like volcanoes, or human-made like pyramids and underground tunnels.

Creating an image in muon tomography starts from measuring tracks of individual cosmic-ray muons. Charged particle tracks are precisely measured by tracking detectors in high-energy physics and muon radiography applications. These detectors come in various types, including gaseous detectors, scintillators, and silicon strip detectors. Scintillation fibers are used in particle tracking detectors to detect charged particles by producing flashes of light (scintillation) when particles pass through them. These fibers offer high precision in tracking particle paths and are particularly valuable in experiments where fine spatial resolution and high-speed detection are required, such as in high-energy physics and medical imaging applications. Gaseous detectors record particle paths by amplifying ionization signals. Drift tubes and drift chambers rely on the measurement of electron drift times in gas-filled volumes to determine particle positions and trajectories. Silicon strip detectors use layers of semiconductor strips to detect ionization caused by charged particles, offering high spatial resolution.

Regardless of the detector type, their primary functions as particle tracking devices include recording the trajectories of charged particles with high precision and providing spatial information about particle paths. Timing characteristics are also crucial for resolving multiple particle tracks and filtering out background noise. For practical applications, factors such as the cost of the technology, scalability, robustness, and ease of use become the primary drivers for selecting the appropriate detector technology. In the context of muon tomography, commercially successful systems are primarily constructed using drift tubes.

Drift tubes, in their early form, were originally developed and introduced in the mid-20th century as part of the ongoing advancements in particle physics and nuclear research. The concept of drift chambers, which includes drift tubes, was pioneered in the 1950s and 1960s to track charged particles and measure their properties accurately. These early developments contributed significantly to the field of high-energy physics and particle tracking, and drift tubes have since evolved and found applications in various experiments, including those at particle accelerators and in muon radiography. These detectors are cylindrical gas-filled tubes, typically ~ 5 cm in diameter and ranging from 1 to 7 meters in length. They operate on the

principle of ionization and electron drift: charged particles ionize the gas atoms, creating electron-ion pairs, and the resulting electrons drift toward a central wire electrode along the tube's axis. Drift tubes provide sub-millimeter spatial resolution along their diameter, offering one-dimensional coordinate measurements. Common gases used include argon, helium, or customized mixtures tailored to specific experiments, ensuring efficient electron drift and precise position measurements. Timing characteristics are essential for spatial accuracy and event selection, with practical drift times measured in hundreds of nanoseconds with an accuracy of a few nanoseconds. Each drift tube incorporates a readout system comprising front-end electronics, which includes amplifiers, discriminators, and time-to-digital converters (TDCs) or analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). These electronics digitize and process amplified signals, extracting precise timing and positional information, thereby enabling the accurate reconstruction of particle trajectories. The electronics are integral to the data acquisition system, vital for high-resolution particle tracking. For practical applications, the cost of electronics is a significant factor, often contributing substantially to the total system cost. However, modern mass-produced electronics boards are both cost-effective and optimized for muon tomography systems, considering characteristics and production expenses. Reliability is paramount, particularly in specialized power supplies. It's noteworthy that muon tomography systems require precise synchronization among the signals collected from individual drift tubes.

Drift tube technology is both mature and robust. These systems have been proven to operate effectively in diverse climates and temperature conditions for extended periods without the need for extensive maintenance and support. A significant feature of commercially viable systems is the utilization of sealed drift tubes, eliminating the need for gas refills after their production. Other important considerations include the non-flammability and non-toxicity of the gases used. During operation, commercially available drift-tube systems consume minimal electrical power and emit no ionizing radiation, making them entirely safe for the human operators and general public.

Muon tomography imaging involves two main steps: trajectory reconstruction and material characteristic calculation. Initially, muon detectors record muon trajectories through the object, capturing data on their paths and interaction points. Techniques like Point of Closest Approach (PoCA) and Maximum Likelihood Expectation-Maximization (MLEM) are commonly used for trajectory reconstruction [5]. The PoCA algorithm estimates the trajectory of muons and intersections within the object by approximating a multiple scattering process with a single-point scattering at the point defined by the incoming and outgoing tracks. It is a simple and intuitive algorithm, which performs quite well when applied to strong scatterers in a low density environments. It is much less efficient however when the object has a variety of distributed densities. The more computationally demanding MLEM algorithm iteratively refines the image by comparing the measured data with simulated projections. This technique provides a quantitative approach to optimizing the image

reconstruction process. While theoretically well-justified, the implementation of MLEM algorithm can be slow and affected by the practical experimental restrictions, in particular, low signal statistics combined with rare high-scattering trajectories that create unrealistically large scattering estimates even in low-density backgrounds. In practice, the efficiency of MLEM algorithm often depends on regularizations and optimizations applied to it. Variety of different modifications to both PoCA and MLEM algorithms have been explored to overcome their deficiencies and limitations. Final choice of the algorithm typically depends on the specific application requirements and detector configuration.

Once trajectories are reconstructed, data is analyzed to calculate material characteristics such as the scattering density. This step is essential for generating meaningful three-dimensional images. Statistical measures like mean and median, along with complex models like multi-Gaussian approximation, are employed for material property estimation [6, 7].

While described here as a two-step process, reconstruction steps are often performed simultaneously or iteratively. Incorporating machine learning algorithms holds promise in improving image quality, accuracy, and resolution. These algorithms streamline data processing, addressing time constraints relevant to applications like border security. They also enhance adaptability to diverse environmental conditions and optimize system design, reducing implementation costs and improving cost-effectiveness. Machine learning continuously enhances muon tomography's practicality and efficiency, aligning it with cutting-edge technology.

III. METHODS: MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR MUON IMAGING

Sufficiently detailed three-dimensional muon tomography images often take a long time to create, limiting the practical applications of muon technology due to these time constraints.

Fig. 2. CNN architecture based on U-NET used for machine learning techniques presented in this paper. While general architecture of the implementation is as shown, image sizes and other details have been modified to adapt to specific tasks and images available.

To address this challenge, Image Acceleration, a set of models developed by Decision Sciences, has been introduced [8]. These models aim to expedite the reconstruction process by generating realistic and accurate predictions for a 10-minute reconstruction based on just 1 minute of reconstruction data. The Image Acceleration model utilizes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on the U-NET architecture [9] (see Fig.2). The U-NET architecture, named after its encoder-decoder structure, incorporates skip connections that effectively bridge the feature maps between the encoder and decoder, facilitating the integration of both low-level and high-level feature representations. Using this architecture the machine learning model was trained with 1-minute reconstructed images as an input and 10-minute reconstructions as an output/prediction. Image acceleration approach has the potential to significantly reduce the time required for muon tomography reconstructions, thereby expanding the range of applications for muon technology.

Muon tomography images often exhibit a notable blur when compared to X-ray images. They lack the sharp, distinct edges that are commonly seen in X-ray imaging. The physical origin of this blur is two-fold. First, the number of particles used to create a muon image is relatively small. Second, the scattering process itself creates a spatial blur in the image. This characteristic can pose challenges for operators and analysts, as it makes the interpretation of muon tomography images more complex. To address this issue, an image enhancement technique known as edge sharpening is applied to muon tomography reconstructions. Edge sharpening involves the application of a mask over the existing reconstruction. This mask is designed as a three-class semantic segmentation model, which is modeled and trained to recognize different classes of materials within the image (air, light materials, steel and other heavier materials). The model generates predictions per voxel, which are then binarized to create a mask that is subsequently applied to the muon tomography image.

The edge sharpening process developed by Decision Sciences also utilizes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on the U-NET architecture, which operates in segmentation mode. This CNN takes the original 10-minute

Fig. 3. Image acceleration example [8]. *Top panel:* Image reconstruction of 60 seconds of muon tomography data in false colors representing scattering density. *Bottom panel:* Prediction of 10-minutes exposure of the same scene with notably reduced level of noise and statistical uncertainty.

muon tomography reconstruction as input and generates the mask. The mask enhances the visual clarity of edges and boundaries within the image, making it easier for operators to interpret and analyze the content. This edge sharpening technique improves the quality and distinctiveness of features in muon tomography images, enhancing their utility for various applications in the field, from security to materials

Fig. 4. Horizontal axis: Measurements of the signal for different materials obtained from 10-minute measurement with the muon tomography scanner. Vertical axis: Same values obtained from 1-minute model predictions. Red line shows ideal correlation between these values. The list of materials includes air, tobacco, ivory, water, paper, salt, concrete, steel, lead, and tungsten.

characterization and beyond. While same basic architecture of the network has been used for both image acceleration and edge sharpening, the last layer of the network was continuous for image acceleration, but discrete for edge sharpening, as well as for human detection technique discussed below.

Another application of machine learning techniques has been recently developed for human detection. Detecting humans hidden in cargo is crucial for national security, preventing human trafficking, ensuring health and safety, upholding immigration laws, and managing economic and resource impacts. It helps maintain lawful and orderly migration, protecting both individuals and society. From muon tomography perspective the problem with human detection is in distinguishing humans from water and organic materials such as fruits, vegetables and meat, often present in border traffic. In spite of the significant challenge, an attempt has been made to develop a machine learning solution to this problem. The approach in this case was to recognize humans as “human material”, which combines physical properties, such as density and elemental composition with some recognition of specific human shapes. In developing the model, previous experience with material models has been extensively used. Human detection is implemented as binary semantic segmentation, using the same UNET architecture as Image Sharpening. The output is a binary mask, indicating which voxels are predicted to be humans. By using the “human material” approach the problem was reduced to a well-known classification problem that has been extensively addressed in recent machine learning literature.

IV. RESULTS

In this section we present some results obtained by the applications of machine learning techniques to muon tomography images. The models and data have been both obtained and developed by Decision Sciences, using commercially available and deployed Discovery systems and in-house software. Image reconstruction has been done using proprietary algorithms and software, based on the main principles described in Section II. Machine learning algorithms were implemented in Python using popular publicly available software PyTorch (trademarked by the Linux Foundation) and Tensorflow (trademarked by Google Inc.).

Fig. 5. Top: Reconstructed muon image. Bottom: Same image after applying edge sharpening, with significantly reduced image blur.

Image Acceleration predictions exhibit smoother features and improved material contrast compared to original reconstructions (see an example in Fig.3). Quantitative analysis confirms strong correlation between accelerated predictions and original reconstructions, highlighting the effectiveness of Image Acceleration models in optimizing image quality and speed (see Fig.4). At the same time we note that this technique may have difficulties in distinguishing small image features from statistical noise. As is a general case with muon tomography, imaging of smaller features with better accuracy requires longer exposure times.

To address the challenge of interpreting muon tomography images, an edge sharpening technique has been developed. This edge sharpening technique improves the quality and distinctiveness of features in muon tomography images, enhancing their utility for various applications in the field, from security to materials characterization and beyond. As an example, consider Fig. 5 with the processed image at the top, which represents a muon tomography reconstruction. Below it, you can observe the same reconstruction with the edge sharpening mask applied. The impact of this mask is evident in the reduced noise emanating from the denser regions of the object under examination, such as a truck. The enhanced clarity and reduced noise levels achieved through edge sharpening significantly improve the interpretability and usability of muon tomography images, making them more effective. We found however that our models had difficulties in simultaneously identifying correctly light materials and calculating correct scattering density values for steel. Our loss function has been optimized to properly identify low-density materials, even though it resulted in the decrease of measurement accuracy for steel (qualitatively, steel objects could be still easily distinguished in the images from the low-density objects).

Human detection approach based on machine learning also has shown a significant promise when applied to muon tomography reconstruction scenes involving humans [10]. Our exploratory studies indicate that the networks learn to distinguish humans based on shape and reconstruction values. Notably, the scenes also contained other materials (e.g., bottled water and frozen meat) that are expected to be close to humans in their physical properties (density, elemental composition, scattering length). Nevertheless, “human material” was identified in the scenes and automatically highlighted based on the predictions of machine learning models (see Fig.6 for one example). Based on this work, Decision Sciences assesses that a limited data collection can result in ~85% detection with ~25% false positive rates at a scan time of 5 minutes. These quantitative estimates should be treated as preliminary and will be refined as more relevant data is collected and the models continue to be trained and optimized.

V. CONCLUSION

While cosmic-ray tomography excels in material discrimination [11, 12], accurately identifying organic and low-Z materials has posed well-known challenges [13]. Our recent testing results signify a substantial progress in this domain, offering renewed hope for the reliable detection of human

Fig. 6. Example of human detection in CRT image [10]. *Top*: The humans are difficult to detect in the original muon tomography image because of their similarity based on physical properties to other objects in the scene (horizontal projection of the reconstructed image is shown). *Bottom*: Application of the machine learning model to human detection in the same scene (vertical and horizontal projections). Highlighted in red are image voxels that are identified by ML/AI model as ‘human material’.

presence concealed within containers and cargo with heightened accuracy and confidence.

Machine learning algorithms hold the potential to enhance various facets of the muon reconstruction pipeline, extending beyond image post-processing. Machine learning algorithms offer significant potential for enhancing muon tomography applications in maritime security. These algorithms can play a crucial role in improving the quality and efficiency of the muon reconstruction pipeline. Machine learning techniques aid in filtering and imputing hits data, effectively reducing noise and ensuring comprehensive datasets for accurate analysis. They can also optimize track fitting processes, enhancing reconstruction precision and computational efficiency. By expediting real-time analysis, machine learning-driven optimizations contribute to bolstering maritime security measures, making muon tomography a valuable tool for detecting threats and ensuring the safety and resilience of international ports. The implementation of reliable human detection capability within maritime security frameworks will enhance the ability to uncover illicit activities such as human trafficking, stowaways, and unauthorized access to vessels, thus fortifying the safety and integrity of maritime operations and infrastructure.

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VI. REFERENCES

- [1] INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Muon Imaging, IAEA-TECDOC-2012, IAEA, Vienna (2022).
- [2] K.N. Borozdin et al. Radiographic imaging with cosmic-ray muons. *Nature* 422, 277 (2003).
- [3] H. Miyadera and C.L. Morris, "Muon scattering tomography: review", *Appl. Opt.* 61, C154-C161 (2022).
- [4] "Nuclear detection system deployed at Freeport," *World Cargo News* (August 10, 2012).
- [5] L. J. Schultz, et al., "Image reconstruction and material Z discrimination via cosmic ray muon radiography," *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. A* 519(3), 687-694 (2004).
- [6] C. L. Morris et al., "Tomographic imaging with cosmic ray muons", *Sci. Glob. Secur.* 16(1-2), 37-53 (2008).
- [7] S. Pesente et al., "First results on material identification and imaging with a large-volume muon tomography prototype" *Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A* 604(3), 738-746 (2009).
- [8] K. Borozdin, R. Vozdolska, J. Kefalos, and A. Crego, "Muon Imaging Methods and Applications," in *Optica Imaging Congress (3D, COSI, DH, FLaOptics, IS, pcAOP)*, Technical Digest Series (Optica Publishing Group), paper HTu5D.2 (2023).
- [9] Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P., and Brox, T. "U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation," In: Navab, N., Hornegger, J., Wells, W., Frangi, A. (eds) *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention. MICCAI 2015. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*(), vol 9351. Springer, Cham (2015).
- [10] BusinessWire News "Decision Sciences International Corporation Announces Breakthrough, Passive Human Detection Capability for Discovery®", Poway CA, March 25, 2024 (<https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20240325573573/en/>)
- [11] S. Vanini et al., "Muography of different structures using muon scattering and absorption algorithms", *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* 377, 20180051 (2018).
- [12] C. L. Morris et al., "Obtaining material identification with cosmic ray radiography", *AIP Advances* 2, 042128 (2012).
- [13] S. Barnes, A. Georgadze, A. Giammanco, M. Kiisk, V.A. Kudryavtsev, M. Lagrange, O.L. Pinto. "Cosmic-Ray Tomography for Border Security", *Instruments*, 7, 13 (2023).